

FOURTH ANNUAL REPORT

for the period

ending June 30, 1960

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, *Inc.*

VIII. Description of the Process to be observed in making large Sheets of Paper, in the Chinese Manner, with one smooth Surface. Communicated by Dr. B. FRANKLIN.

From the TRANSACTIONS of the AMERICAN PHILOSOPHICAL SOCIETY.

IN Europe to have a large surface of paper connected together, and smooth on one side, the following operations are performed :

1. A number of small sheets are to be made separately.

2. These are to be couched, one by one, between blankets.

3. When a heap is formed, it must be put under a strong press, to force out the water.

4. Then the blankets are to be taken away, one by one, and the sheets hung up to dry.

VOL. I.

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ANNUAL
REPORT *for the period ending June 30,*
1960

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, *Inc.*

1025 CONNECTICUT AVENUE, N.W.

WASHINGTON, D. C.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

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* Through November 12, 1959. Dr. Weaver was succeeded by Dr. James S. Coles, President of Bowdoin College, on November 9, 1960.

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in 1956 in the District of Columbia, with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

The Council's Fourth Year

“INFORMATION STORAGE

AND RETRIEVAL” and

The Problems of Libraries

When the Council on Library Resources was established in 1956, “information storage and retrieval” was still a phrase of art in the vocabulary of documentalists. Today it is a byword that can be overheard in Pullman cars and in airplanes; industrial corporations assign research and development funds to the exploration of its problems; it has become the subject of a recent article in *Fortune*.¹

The phrase doubtless performs a useful role in calling attention to an important group of problems—those which surround the exploitation of recorded information, whether in or outside of libraries. These problems, so neglected until recently by most of those to whom they should have been of major concern, now receive important attention. This attention reached new heights during the year just past. Several evidences are worthy of mention.

Even before the opening of the year there were three current lists of research in progress in the field of “information storage and retrieval”²; their emphasis is on scientific and technical information, especially as communicated by mechanical and electronic means. During the year a new list appeared, reporting on current research and development in the field of library

¹ Francis Bello: How to Cope with Information. *Fortune* 62:162-167, 180, 182, 187, 189, 192 (September 1960).

² *Current Research and Development in Scientific Documentation* (Washington, D. C.: Office of Science Information Service, U. S. National Science Foundation, July 1957—. Semiannual). No. 7 (November 1960) lists under 154 headings a much larger number of research projects.

Non-conventional Information Technical Systems in Current Use (Washington, D. C.: Office of Science Information Service, U. S. National Science Foundation, January 1958—. Irregular). No. 2 (September 1959) and its Supplement (March 1960) list systems reported by 52 organizations.

Scientific Information Notes (formerly *Science Information News*) (Washington, D. C.: U. S. National Science Foundation, February-March 1959—. Bimonthly).

work generally³. As a result it is now possible to gauge much more accurately than previously how much effort is going into searches for solutions to the "information problem."

During the year, too, the National Academy of Sciences-National Research Council (which had participated as an observer in the Royal Society's Conference on Scientific Information, London, 1948, but which had — with assistance from the Council — actively co-sponsored the International Conference on Scientific Information, Washington, 1958) established an Office of Documentation and became almost immediately thereafter the American affiliate of the International Federation for Documentation. A tiny membership organization — the American Institute for Documentation — was thus relieved of the burden of this representation. At the same time the Academy-Council established a U. S. National Committee for the International Federation for Documentation, so as to assure full representation of American interest in the endeavor. Simultaneously, too, the heightened interest in documentation on both sides of the Atlantic promise for the Federation — the international organization in this field of work — a much-needed invigoration.

During the past year, too, the United States Senate, pursuing a continuing interest in improving the bases of scientific work in the national interest, issued through one of its committees a staff study of programs for the processing and retrieval of scientific information both within and outside the Federal Government,⁴ and a committee of the House of Representatives held public hearings on machine translation.⁵

Many other similar evidences might be mentioned.

How, in the light of this increased attention to the "information problem," and in view of the greatly improved situation

³ *Library Research in Progress* (Washington, D. C.: Library Services Branch, Office of Education, U. S. Department of Health, Education and Welfare, October 1959—. Irregular). No. 3 (April 1960) reports 52 projects.

⁴ *Documentation, Indexing and Retrieval of Scientific Information. A Study of Federal and Non-Federal Science Information Processing and Retrieval Programs Prepared by the Staff of the Committee on Government Operations, United States Senate*. Washington: U. S. Government Printing Office, 1960. 283 p. (86th Congress, 2nd Session, Senate Document 113.)

⁵ *Research on Mechanical Translation. Report of the Committee on Science and Astronautics, U. S. House of Representatives*. Washington: U. S. Government Printing Office, 1960. 51 p. (86th Congress, 2nd Session, House Report 2021.)

with respect to coordination of work in the field and of the considerable sums of money being expended upon research and development in it—how do the “problems of libraries” and the attempts to solve them stand? How much closer to solution are these problems than they were in 1956 when the Council was established?

Several facts seem to emerge from the enormous amount of discussion, research and reporting which surrounds this subject.

The Computers

Note may be taken, in the first place, of the nature of much of the present effort toward solution of the “information problem.” It is to a large degree computer-oriented. The extraordinary capabilities of these machines in manipulating numeric and alphabetic data and in simulating complex clerical and even intellectual operations make it imperative that their potentialities for information work be exploited. But when the attempt is made to employ them in this work, it is found that the tasks of preparing them for their new duties are massive.

Considerations of logic, classification theory, syntax and meaning occur of course in the construction of every index and every card catalog. But these are as nothing when the same informational content is prepared for a computer. For this reason, much of the current work on the “information problem” has been concerned with the problems of linguistics (using that term in a broad sense) encountered in employing computers for information work. This has had still another effect. In order to find manageable fields of investigation, inquiries are typically restricted to special subject areas, such as metallurgy, steroid chemical compounds, cancer chemotherapy, etc., from which the results are not immediately transferable to other fields of interest.

In a recent review of the applications of computers to the information problem, an observant critic has come to the conclusion that “the outlook for the possible use of computers in information work is thus far from clear. Extant claims for their far-reaching use in this field have not been substantiated either in theory or in practice. Partial uses whose feasibility seems plausible in theory have not been seriously tested as to their economic practicability, and might well require the construction of special purpose devices whose mode of operation

differs rather radically from the one generally accepted at present as being most efficient.”⁶

In spite of this pessimistic conclusion, it may be expected that computer applications to information handling will progressively affect libraries. The following may be foreseen:

First, it may be expected that the assistance of computers will be brought increasingly to situations where their use is justified by the mass and complexity of the information to be handled, and by the economic or operational needs. This is already happening with respect to the exploitation of information in particular fields of physics, chemistry, patent literature and military intelligence. But, as with the special catalogs and indexes traditionally created by libraries for the use of specialized clientele, it may be expected that such applications will remain localized. The principal general effect of these installations will be in demonstrating the economics of the computers, in indicating the parts of the information process which they can most effectively serve, in stimulating general solutions of the linguistic problems involved in their employment, and in encouraging the development of special-purpose devices better suited to the work but less expensive than the general-purpose machines now employed.

Second, it may be expected that computer applications will affect library work indirectly, by making available published indexes and other finding apparatus which would not be feasible without them. We already have concordances made by computer; and during the past year a large professional scientific association experimentally adopted the “permuted index” (a concordance-type listing of the titles of journal articles, compiled by computer) as a method of rapidly and inexpensively disseminating information regarding current research in its field. Such instances will undoubtedly multiply.

Third, it is foreseeable that there will gradually become available a body of material which libraries can use on computers. Although a number of libraries now have access to these devices, few make any use of them. The explanation for this is simply that the cost of preparing the “input” is too great, both in intellectual and physical terms, for individual

⁶ Jehoshua Bar-Hillel: Some Theoretical Aspects of the Mechanization of Literature Searching. [n.p., 1960] (U. S. Office of Naval Research Contract N62558-2214), p. 55.

institutions. But if such input were available from central sources, the situation might change rapidly.

For example, experiments are now going on looking to possible machine searching of the literature of the law. If these experiments should result in a technique which gives results superior to traditional methods, libraries would be under strong pressure to provide the service. But just as the searching apparatus for the traditional methods of searching the literature of the law is now purchased from publishers, it may be expected that the input tapes and programs for performing such searches by computer would be purchased from central services.

And so with many other of the operations which libraries perform. It is conceivable that in the future they will be able to purchase information in machinable form to do certain of these operations better.⁷ For example, if booksellers' catalogs could be consolidated in machinable language by a central service (making use, perhaps of character-recognition machines), and if suitable "searching" programs could be prepared, the expensive task of "searching" (to ascertain whether or not a desirable book is already represented in the collections) might be performed mechanically. As another example, if the principal indexing services to current journal literature were available in machinable language, a library might make a selection of those parts which index its collection and no more, thus providing a much more convenient searching instrument for its clientele. By the same token, regional bibliographic centers might be able to consolidate the contents of the many thousands of indexing services into a few, thus providing genuinely comprehensive, yet manageable, tools for extensive searches.

Other Developments

In addition to the computer-oriented investigations and the associated studies mentioned above, the current interest in the information problem manifests itself in numerous developments

⁷ It should be remembered that they now purchase information in machinable form, though not for computers. Library of Congress catalog cards, which many libraries now reproduce for their own purposes by photo-offset processes, provide one instance of machinable information; microfilm, which lends itself to mechanical reproduction in microform and even to the re-creation of the image in original size, is another.

which may in due course have considerable effect on library work. Among these may be mentioned especially the attempts to apply high-reduction photography (as well as other techniques for the spatial compression of data) to information systems; the development of improved photocopying techniques and devices; work on "character recognition," *i.e.* the development of machines that can read printed and even manuscript text and convert this text into machinable language; the construction of devices other than computers for mechanizing the processes of identifying sources of information, especially those based on applications of "coordinate" indexing; and improvement of methods of transmitting information at a distance. And, in addition to technological development, there are the attempts to improve the organization of information work, such as by introducing more effective coordination into the activities of the primary publishing agencies and the indexing and abstracting services.

Just as with the computer-oriented studies, most of these developments aim at markets either outside the library field such as the management of business records, or at special manifestations of library work such as the handling of in-house industrial research reports or of military intelligence. There is no doubt, however, that libraries generally will eventually benefit. Indeed, since the establishment of the Council, library work has benefited greatly from the development of office copying devices. One of these in combination with microfilm, has made a major contribution to the solution of the out-of-print book problem.

The Prospects for Library Work

It may thus be expected that the current interest in "information retrieval" will eventually benefit libraries in many ways. There is no doubt, however, that it will in the meantime add to their burdens by increasing the quantities of material for which they must take responsibility. As a matter of fact, it is already doing so. The computers are facilitating the production of index-type books and periodicals which libraries must possess in order to give good service. Translation programs are similarly resulting in the requirement upon many libraries that they subscribe to periodicals simultaneously in both original foreign-language text and in English translation.

Meanwhile, because the current interest in information storage and retrieval is necessarily directed to the problems of specialist groups, it has scarcely touched those problems of libraries which arise from their efforts to serve many groups simultaneously. The new indexing methods are restricted in application and cannot yet replace the card catalog; the major problems of distribution of resources and of the user's access to them have hardly as yet even been felt by these more specialized studies.

Accordingly, there seems to be no reason to expect that the recent rise in interest in the problems of communication through recorded information holds the prospect of an early millennium for libraries. Rather, this interest is symptomatic of a general concern for the benefits to be derived from recorded information which is simultaneously expressed in greater demand upon the services of libraries, resulting in the situation that these are under greater pressure than ever before. The search for solutions to their problems, which include not only problems in the storage and retrieval of information but also problems in the organization of institutions and of nationwide and worldwide systems composed of institutions, must continue to be pressed with vigor.

The Council's Fourth Year

The principal concern of the Council during the fiscal year ending June 30, 1960, was a review of the program during its first three years with a view to evaluating its progress in the task assigned, as well as the need for continuation of the assignment and the prospects of success in it. During the year it made grants and contracts and undertook directly-administered projects involving obligations totalling \$569,211. Also during the period a number of projects matured. The projects newly undertaken and those completed during the year are the subjects of the following pages.

Verner W. Clapp
President

NEW PROJECTS

The year's major new projects are listed briefly below in the topical arrangement which has been found most satisfactory for categorizing the Council's undertakings because it implies the ultimate objectives of the program rather than merely the immediate improvement of recognized departments of library activity such as acquisition or cataloging. Such activities as these, essential as they obviously are to library work as at present conducted, are no more than means to an end. The end, simply stated, is to make it possible to put into the hand of an inquirer, wherever he may be, the source or sources of recorded information which provide the most appropriate response to his inquiry, wherever those sources may be, and with a minimum of delay and expense.

Although the end is thus a single one, there are several principal intermediate steps toward it. The first consists in ascertaining what relevant sources of recorded information exist and whence they may be procured, and in making a selection from them. The second step consists in the procurement of those sources that are selected. But, just as in other distribution of consumer goods, this procurement is for the most part performed in anticipation of the demand rather than following its appearance, and is the object of much of the day-to-day work of libraries.

The third intermediate step between the inquirer and the book is consequently the library itself, or, in general terms, the complex of administrative arrangements through which the first two steps are effected.

In seeking improvements, it is found that there are, generally speaking, only a few methods of attack. They may be broadly characterized as follows:

- a. By seeking more effective coordination of effort, either through superior forms of organization, through the promotion of uniformity of practice as a basis for common effort, or through the development of mechanisms for making coordination feasible.
- b. By improving the tools of the work, whether bibliographical or mechanical, and the resources in personnel.
- c. By increasing the support and financial resources available to the work.

Each of the projects listed below is in consequence to be regarded as part of an effort to improve the efficiency of one or more of the steps identified above, making use of one or more of the methods of attack just described.

Improvement of the Means of Bibliographic Access

(These means include the devices, arrangements and forms of organization through which the existence of a source of recorded information is known, together with the location from which it may be procured or at which it may be consulted. Examples are national bibliographies, publishers' and booksellers' lists, bibliographies, indexes, abstracting services, library catalogs, union catalogs and union lists; the techniques and mechanisms by which these are effected; bibliographic and reference service.)

International Coordination of Cataloging. To enable the International Federation of Library Associations to organize and hold an international conference on the principles of cataloging in Paris in 1961 in fulfillment of the plans laid at the Preliminary Conference in London, 1959 (see page 23). It is expected that representatives of some fifty national groups, a number of national libraries and bibliographic agencies, and individual experts will attend this conference which will seek a basis for agreement on principles from which it is hoped that a useful measure of uniformity of practice may result. A series of working papers is being commissioned. The project is under the direction of the Organizing Committee of IFLA's Working Group on the Coordination of Cataloging Principles, of which the members are Mr. A. H. Chaplin (United Kingdom), M. Paul Poindron (France), Dr. L. Sickmann (Germany), and Mme. N. Lavrova (USSR).

In the interest of the success of the 1961 conference, the Council made it possible for the American Library Association to invite the members of the Organizing Committee to attend the Institute for Catalog Code Revision held by the Association at McGill University in June 1960. A useful exchange of views was achieved.

Khrushchev, Nikita Sergeevich, 1894-

For victory in peaceful competition with capitalism. With a special introd. written for the American ed. New York, Dutton, 1960.

xxxi, 783 p. 21 cm.

"A collection of speeches and statements made in the course of 1958 on various questions relating to the international situation and foreign policy of the Soviet Union."

1. Russia—Relations (general) with foreign countries. I. Title.

DK274.K483

327.47

60-6004

Library of Congress

(40)

F.v.U

Crossman, Richard Howard Stafford, 1907- ed.

New Fabian essays [by] R. H. S. Crossman [and others]; Pref. by C. R. Attlee. New York, F. A. Praeger [1952];

215 p. 23 cm. (Books that matter)

1. Socialism—Addresses, essays, lectures. 2. Economic policy—Addresses, essays, lectures. 3. Socialism in Great Britain. I. Title.

HX246.C88 1952a

335.04

52-10784 †

Library of Congress

(60C1)

Chruščev, N. S.

Le désarmement est la voie du renforcement de la paix et la garantie de l'amitié entre les peuples; (rapport présenté à la session du Soviet Supremé de l'U. R. S. S. le 14 janvier 1960) [Paris, 1960]

Zentralkatalog der ausländischen Literatur

(ZKA)

Essays. - New Fabian Essays, R. H. S. Crossman. . . Pref. by C. R. Attlee. - London: Turnstile Pr. 1952. xv, 215 S.

Zentralkatalog der ausländischen Literatur.

(ZKA)

6037

6037. =KHROUCHTCHEV (Nikita).

— N. Khrouchtchev. *Le Désarmement est la voie du renforcement de la paix et la garantie de l'amitié entre les peuples*, rapport présenté à la session du Soviet suprême de l'U. R. S. S. le 14 janvier 1960. — Paris, G.D.L.P. (Impr. I.C.C.), 1960.

— In-16 (20 cm., 64 p., portrait. [D. L. 1756-69]) —VIII1J28— [16° M. 2625 40]

(Collection « Etudes soviétiques ».)

U. R. S. S. Politique extérieure. 1960, 14 janvier. Texte.

New Fabian essays [by] R. H. S. Crossman [and others]; Pref. by C. R. Attlee. New York, F. A. Praeger [1952]; 215 p. 23 cm. (Books that matter)

Bibl. Nat.

Krushchov, Nikita Serheevich.

Le désarmement est la voie du renforcement de la paix et la garantie de l'amitié entre les peuples; (rapport présenté à la session du Soviet Suprême de l' U. R. S. S. le 14 janvier 1960) [Paris, 1960]

The British National Bibliography

Crossman, Richard Howard Stafford, editor. New Fabian essays; preface by the Rt. Hon. C. R. Attlee. London, Turnstile P., 15/-.. May 1952. xv, 215 p. 22 1/2cm.

BNB (1952), p. 118.

DIVERSITY OF CATALOGING AMONG NATIONS—Two representative titles as catalogued in four nations. Top row: Library of Congress, United States; second row, Union Catalog of Research Libraries of North Rhine, West Germany; third row, Bibliothèque Nationale, France; fourth row, The British Na-

tional Bibliography, United Kingdom. (The French card for the Crossman book is hypothetical but characteristic; all others are actual instances.) Divergencies in cataloging are even greater in the cataloging of government publications, atlases, art exhibition catalogs, and other non-personal works.

Coordination in the Registration of Publications. To make possible a study, under the auspices of the American Library Association, of the feasibility of coding current American publications in a manner which would be simultaneously suitable for the business use of publishers (in inventorying, invoicing, machine accounting, etc.), yet be of assistance in the book-selection and purchasing activities of libraries. This study is being conducted by Mr. Gustave A. Harrer of Stanford University (more recently of Boston University) and Mr. Alex Ladenson, Chicago Public Library.

Registration of Micro-Texts. To enable the Association of Research Libraries to commission a study of the bibliographical control of the microforms. For lack of adequate recording it is now impossible to learn satisfactorily of important materials existing in microfilm, Microcard, Microprint, etc. This results not only in failure to take advantage of their existence, but also in wasteful duplication by copying what has already been copied. The study, directed to improving the situation, is being conducted by Professor Wesley Simonton of the University of Minnesota.

Tools of Book Selection. The Council has continued to study the means whereby a "New Shaw," replacing the obsolete and out-of-print work,¹ might be prepared and maintained as a current book-selection service addressed to college libraries and other libraries having similar needs. The problems involved are administrative, technological and economic. During the year a study of the technological aspects was made by Hubbard W. Ballou of Columbia University. This is now being applied to the further study of the problem.

Mechanization of Bibliographic Operations. To enable the American Association of Law Libraries to make use of automatic camera techniques in the compilation of a list of legal subject headings. The work is being carried on under the supervision of Dr. Werner B. Ellinger of the Library of Congress.

To enable the de Florez Company to make preliminary investigations of the feasibility of constructing a catalog card duplicator. These investigations relate to the problem of

¹ Charles B. Shaw: *A List of Books for College Libraries* [prepared for the Carnegie Corporation of New York]. 2nd preliminary edition. Chicago, American Library Association, 1931. [Supplement], 1931-38, 1940.

printing catalog card stock using wax stencil techniques.

To enable the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association to contract for the development of an efficient catalog card holding accessory for typewriters, and for the development of a device for making the spines of books.

Coordination of Effort in Book-Preparation. To enable the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc. (a cooperative book-processing center serving 13 public library systems) to prepare a brochure descriptive of its services. The Service (in the establishment of which the Council has taken an interest on previous occasions² is noteworthy as a successful "grass-roots" cooperative representing independent local governmental units.³

Improvement of the Means of Physical Access

(These means include the devices, arrangements and forms of organization through which a source of recorded information, once identified and its location known, is put into an inquirer's hands. Examples are the procedures of distribution and acquisition, book storage and preservation, interlibrary lending and photocopying.)

Planning of Acquisition. To enable the American Council of Learned Societies to procure a report, to be prepared by its Deputy Director, Emeritus, Mr. Mortimer Graves, on the status of arrangements for the procurement of foreign publications under the provisions of the Agricultural Trade Development Assistance Act of 1954 as amended ("Public Law 480"⁴).

² II: 18-19; III:45. (Citations in this form are to the Council's annual reports; in this case to its *Second Annual Report*, pages 18 and 19, and to the *Third Annual Report*, page 45.)

³ Two of the most recent articles — both by Willard K. Dennis, President of the organization — on this subject are: "Central Processing in Southwest Missouri," *Library Journal*, 84: 3378-3380, November 1, 1959, and "A Unique Cataloging and Processing Centre (USA)," *Unesco Bulletin for Libraries*, 14: 173-174, July - August, 1960.

⁴ Mortimer Graves: "A First Anniversary Report on the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to Public Law 480 (Title I, Section 104n)," [American Council of Learned Societies] *ACLS Newsletter* 10: 8-12. November 1959. Also: *An Addendum Report on the Implementation of the Dingell Amendment to Public Law 480*. Key West, Florida, The Author, March 1960. 4 pp.

To make possible a study, to be conducted under the sponsorship of the American Council of Learned Societies by Dr. Lester Born, looking to the identification of criteria for establishing priorities for scholarly photocopying projects. There is reason to believe that available funds for photocopying materials needed for scholarly research are not now being put to best use, and that additional funds might be made available if the planning of photocopying projects could be put on a sounder basis.

Use of Library Space. To enable the Yale University Library to complete the study commenced the previous year⁵ of the bases and results of its selective book retirement program.

To assist the Library of Congress in evaluating the use of shelf-classification on its book-stacks. The Library of Congress maintains the world's most elaborate book classification; the printed schedules which merely present it occupy an entire shelf. The classification is costly to maintain and apply, and the cost of stack administration is increased through its use. Its justification is in providing an important method of access to the collections, but more needs to be known to enable a judgement to be drawn as to whether its usefulness justifies its cost. The project, to be carried out by the firm of Herner & Company, Washington, D. C., will design a study of the use of classified collections, test the design in application to the collection of the Library of Congress, sample the types and usefulness of the results that might emerge from a definitive study, and estimate the cost of such a study.

Copying. To procure the working model of an automatic book-cradle/page-turner to be designed and constructed by the de Florez Company, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, N.J. The book-holders used in book-copying work typically require the book to open completely flat (too often with the use of force), and do not permit it to rest in a natural position (*e.g.*, opened at a 90° angle). The device to be constructed will permit copying in such a position while the pages are turned automatically. The device will be tested for application to microfilming and telefacsimile copying of books.

Personal Use of Microcopy. To procure the design of a high-power magnifier for use in a hand-reader for micro-opaques. (See Appendix.)

⁵ III:33.

LIBRARY TECHNOLOGY PROJECT — Laminating equipment is tested in the laboratory.

Book Preservation. To enable the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association to test certain materials and processes used in book preservation, including laminating equipment and adhesives.

To enable representatives of the American Library Association and Special Libraries Association to plan a program for establishing performance standards for bookbinding. The resultant plan was under consideration by the Council at the end of the year.

Telecommunication of Library Materials. One of the Council's earliest grants was for a demonstration of the application of closed-circuit TV in a decentralized library situation.⁶ This project identified a number of points at which improvements would be necessary before such installations might become genuinely useful. During the past year a review of the situation was commenced in a contract with Image Instruments, Inc., Boston, Mass., for inventorying and evaluating the various equipment and channels which might be applied to improving the utilization of library resources in a metropolitan area by electronic telecommunication.

⁶ I:22-23.

PROVIDENCE PUBLIC LIBRARY — Because of the inadequacy of school libraries, public libraries are overrun by students.

Improvement of the Administrative Bases of Library Work

(Under this head are included those arrangements which bring the means of bibliographic and of physical access to the service of the inquirer. Examples are the planning of library buildings, library administration and finance, training of staff, and interlibrary cooperation.)

Library Administration. To Emory University to enable its librarian, Dr. Guy R. Lyle, to complete the text for a new edition of his work, *The Administration of College Libraries*.

Coordination of Resources and Services. To make possible a study, under the sponsorship of Brown University, in support of a project in university-school-community library coordination with the objective of improving instruction in Rhode Island. The project, which is under the supervision of Dean Elmer R. Smith of the Master of Arts in Teaching Program at Brown, will be directed by Mr. John A. Humphry of the Springfield (Massachusetts) Library and Museums Association.

To enable a group of the larger libraries of Maine (Bates, Bowdoin and Colby Colleges, University of Maine, Bangor and Portland Public Libraries and the Maine State Library) to procure a survey—to be conducted by Mr. Keyes D. Metcalf, Director Emeritus of the Harvard University Library

— to explore the bases for strengthening the resources and services of these libraries by cooperative undertakings.

To enable the American Library Association's Committee on Metropolitan Area Library Service to plan a study of the jurisdictional and other problems of providing library service in metropolitan areas. A small grant permitted the Committee to seek consultative assistance from experts in metropolitan area problems.

Library Buildings. To make it possible for the Association of Research Libraries and the Association of College and Research Libraries to provide financial and advisory support for the preparation of a book on the planning of college and university library buildings by Mr. Keyes D. Metcalf so as to draw upon his unequalled experience with library building problems. It is anticipated that the preparation of the book will direct attention to needed research, some of which, it is hoped, may be carried out while the book is in progress. Individual chapters of the book will be reviewed for accuracy by architectural and engineering experts in the several fields.

Book Circulation. A preliminary inquiry into the record-keeping problems of book circulation systems by John Diebold & Associates was intended to identify the portion of the field lending itself to most profitable further study. This inquiry was completed during the year and a report has been published⁷.

A contract was later placed with George Fry & Associates to conduct an inquiry into book-circulation systems with a view to identifying and/or developing methods of book-charging of maximum simplicity and economy consistent with effective control. A grant was made simultaneously to enable the American Library Association to establish an advisory committee on the project under the chairmanship of Mr. Forrest Carhart, Assistant Director of the Library Technology Project.

"Library Technology." This term has come to designate programs of testing and standardization of library supplies and equipment, the dissemination of purchasing information, and the development of improved devices for the performance of library operations. In addition to several grants for specific

⁷ John Diebold and Associates, Inc.: *Preliminary Study of Library Circulation Systems for the Council on Library Resources*, October 1959. The Corporation, 1959. 31 ll. Also issued as a Microcard.

developments, mentioned above, a grant was made to the American Library Association for the general strengthening of its Library Technology Project.

Support of Libraries. To enable the National Book Committee to undertake a special training program in connection with National Library Week. This program, directed to library groups, was intended to develop and implement the techniques of exploiting the resources of citizen interests for library support so as to enable libraries increasingly to take over the planning and managing of the National Library Week effort, integrating it into year round activities. In cooperation with the American Library Association and local groups, the Committee held four leadership training workshops in various parts of the country, August-January 1960, in preparation for National Library Week 1960, and revised and reissued its two principal instructional manuals⁸.

To enable the Association of Research Libraries to convene two meetings of the research contract officers and librarians of a number of universities to develop a general applicable formula for determining the charges representing the library contribution which should be included in Government research contracts. If successful, this effort will remove a long-standing problem.

Fact-Finding for Planning and Research

The Effect of Population Trends on Library Work. The April 1961 issue of *Library Trends* will consider the impact of demographic trends on libraries. A small grant to the University of Illinois will make it possible for Professor Philip M. Hauser of the University of Chicago, who will prepare the lead article for the issue, to analyze raw data from the 1960 Census for its bearing on the subject.

The Library of the Future. The American Library Association has been invited by the Century 21 International Exposi-

⁸ *Open Wonderful New Worlds . . . Wake Up and Read! National Library Week Organization Handbook.* [New York: The Committee, 1960.] 56 pp. *3rd Annual Report, For a Better-Read, Better-Informed America, 1960 National Library Week.* [New York: The Committee, 1960.] 24 pp.

tion, Seattle, 1962, to prepare an exhibit of the library of the future. A small grant made it possible for the Association to procure a survey by Mr. Joseph W. Becker of the feasibility of preparing such an exhibit, drawing assistance from electronic data-processing mechanisms and other devices of automation. Mr. Becker reported favorably and a plan for the actual planning of such an exhibit was under consideration at the close of the year.

Barriers to the Booktrade in the Americas. The Pan American Union (the secretariat of the Organization of American States) proposes to place on the agenda of the 11th Inter-American Conference, Quito, 1961, the question of improving the flow of published information among the American republics. The Council has assisted the Union to secure a study, conducted by Mr. Peter Jennison of New York University and Mr. William H. Kurth of the National Library of Medicine, of the obstacles which will require abatement if the objective is to be achieved. The report of this study has been published⁹.

PROJECTS COMPLETED

During the year a number of the Council's projects were completed to the extent that work undertaken under specific grants or contracts was executed. Where work was completed on a project initiated during the year, results are reported in the previous chapter. For projects initiated previously, work completed during the past year is briefly noted below.

"Targets for Research." The project designated as "Targets for Research in Library Work" was the first of the Council's major projects.¹⁰ It was conducted under a grant to Rutgers University to enable Dean (then Professor) Ralph R. Shaw of its Graduate School of Library Service to survey, with the aid of a team of experts drawn from many institutions, the "state of the library art" and to conclude therefrom the directions in which research in library problems might be most profitably directed. There have resulted from this survey a series of 18 studies, which are now in the process of publi-

⁹ Peter S. Jennison and William H. Kurth. *Books in the Americas: A Study of the Principal Barriers to the Booktrade in the Americas.* Washington: Pan American Union, General Secretariat, Organization of American States, 1960. 165 pp. Processed. (Estudios Bibliotecarios N. 2.)

¹⁰ I:19

cation by the Graduate School and are being distributed by the Rutgers University Press. Five books have now appeared ¹¹.

Standards of Cataloging. Under a grant made in 1958,¹² the International Federation of Library Associations held a preliminary meeting in London in July 1959 to plan an international conference on the principles of cataloging. There was representation from some 15 countries. It was concluded that conditions are favorable for seeking wide agreement on cataloging principles, and a basis in organization and agenda was laid for a conference to be held in 1961. The final report was published in *Libri* and the *Unesco Bulletin for Libraries* ¹³. This project led directly to the present plans for a conference in 1961 (see page 13).

Mechanization of Library Operations. The first phase of the project in machine indexing conducted by Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc.¹⁴ was completed in April 1960, and a final report was then rendered ¹⁵. Since the end of the year the substance of the report has appeared in an article by the principal investigator for the project, Dr. Don R. Swanson ¹⁶. The results of this project cannot be adequately summarized here;

¹¹ Ralph R. Shaw: series editor: *The State of the Library Art*. New Brunswick, N.J., Graduate School of Library Service, Rutgers — The State University, 1960. Volume 1, Part 1, *Cataloging and Classification*, by Maurice F. Tauber; Volume 1, Part 2, *Subject Headings*, by Carlyle J. Frarey; 271 and 92 pp. Volume 2, Part 1, *Training Laymen in Use of the Library*, by George S. Bonn; Volume 2, Part 2, *Bibliographies, Abstracts and Indexes*, by Margaret S. Bryant; 114 and 108 pp. Volume 3, Part 1, *Buildings*, by Ralph E. Ellsworth; Volume 3, Part 2, *Shelving*, by Louis Kaplan; Volume 3, Part 3, *Storage Warehouses*, by Jerrold Orne; 151, 41 and 52 pp. Volume 5, Part 1, *Production of Micro-Forms*, by Reginald Hawkins; 208 pp. Volume 5, Part 2, *Reading Devices for Micro-Images*, by Jean Stewart, Doralyn Hickey and others; 205 pp.

¹² II:10-11.

¹³ "IFLA [International Federation of Library Associations] International Cataloging Conference, Preliminary Meeting, London, July 19th-25th, 1959, Report," *Libri* 9: 254-261. 1959. "International Cataloging Conference, 1961," *Unesco Bulletin for Libraries* 14: May-June 1960, 136. Also, "Moving Toward International Cataloging Agreement," by Susan M. Haskins, *ALA Bulletin* 54: 197-201, March 1960; Wyllis E. Wright: "International Cataloging Conference." *Library Resources and Technical Services* 4: 85-89. Winter, 1960.

¹⁴ III:26-28.

¹⁵ Ramo-Wooldridge, Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc.: Word Correlation and Automatic Indexing, Phase I, Final Report, "An Experiment in Automatic Text Searching," C82-QU4, 30 April, 1960. Canoga Park, California, The Corporation, [1960]. [45 ll., and three separately bound supplements], Processed.

¹⁶ Don R. Swanson: "Searching Natural Language Text by Computer," *Science* 132: 1099-1104. October 21, 1960.

it may be noted, however, that the computer method of searching was able to identify 86% of the "source documents" in response to a series of questions, whereas a group of librarians who had cataloged the same material was able to recover only 38%. These results appeared sufficiently promising that at the end of the year the Council was preparing to authorize the second phase of the project.

"*Cataloging-in-Source.*" In May 1958 the Library of Congress undertook a study of the feasibility of the bibliographic service which has come to be known as "cataloging-in-source."¹⁷ This phrase describes the situation in which books are cataloged prior to publication and the resulting cataloging data are printed in the books themselves. It has been conjectured that such a service might greatly reduce cataloging costs by providing libraries with the necessary cataloging information at the moment of the receipt of the book, thus avoiding the necessity either for cataloging it themselves or for procuring cataloging information from another source. It has also been thought that cataloging-in-source would be useful to others than librarians — to all who cite books, by providing a standard form of citation; and to booksellers and book collectors by providing a shelf-classification symbol in the book itself which would make book collections self arranging.

In order to test these assumptions as well as the feasibility of the operation itself, the Library of Congress undertook to make arrangements with publishers which would permit the cataloging of approximately one thousand publications on the basis of page or galley proofs and the printing of the resulting catalog entries in the books as published; that the results should be analyzed; and that a survey should be made to ascertain the reaction of librarians to the experiment. This survey was undertaken with the advisory assistance of the Cataloging Policy and Research Committee of the American Library Association.

The report of the project was received in April, 1960¹⁸ It is an impressive document, recording the results of an admirably conducted experiment which in its execution surpassed all reasonable expectations. Over a period of eight months 1,203

¹⁷ II:15-18.

¹⁸ *The Cataloging-in-Source Experiment, A Report to the Librarian of Congress by the Director of the Processing Department.* Washington, Library of Congress, 1960. xxiv, 199 pp.

publications of 157 publishers were cataloged prior to publication. The Library was able by a prodigious effort to give substantially a 24-hour turn-around service in the cataloging. Most of the publishers questioned at the conclusion of the experiment indicated that they would be willing to cooperate in a continuing program if it provided a useful service to libraries. The consumer reaction survey, on the other hand, made plain the desire of a representative group of American libraries for the service, although the limited character of the experiment did not permit clear-cut evidence of the savings that might be effected. As for the technical feasibility of cataloging books prior to publication, it was found that no less than 58% of the books were cataloged with complete accuracy; while of the errors in the 42% almost half were discrepancies in collation, principally in the statements of the number of pages and the size of the book — facts which are, however, manifest when a copy of the book is in hand.

The report concludes, nevertheless, that a permanent, full-scale program of cataloging-in-source would not be justified. The grounds given for this conclusion are the high costs of cataloging-in-source to publishers and to the Library, its disruption of publishers' schedules, the high degree of unreliability of the resulting catalog entries and their consequent low utility.

Toward the end of the year the report was receiving discussion¹⁹.

Distribution and Acquisition of Publications. In 1958 the Council made it possible for the United States Book Exchange, Inc., to conduct a survey of its operations²⁰. The Exchange, which is located in Washington, D. C., is a non-profit enterprise supported by library and other learned groups for making use of library duplicates in both domestic and foreign exchange. The survey was conducted by Mr. Edwin E. Williams, Associate Librarian of Harvard University. His report appeared at the beginning of the year²¹. It provided a number of recom-

¹⁹ For example: Orcena Mahoney: "Cataloging in Source," *ALA Bulletin* 54: 197-201. March 1960.

²⁰ II:22.

²¹ Edwin E. Williams: *A Serviceable Reservoir: Report of a Survey of the United States Book Exchange*. Washington: The United States Book Exchange, Inc., 1959. 81 pp. Also by the same author: "The U.S.B.E. Survey," *Library Resources and Technical Services* 4: 89-91. Winter, 1960.

PAPER RESEARCH—Above, W. J. Barrow tests the folding endurance of paper. Below, The graph illustrates the resistance to tear or rupture (in grams of force) after different periods of artificial aging. (Heating at 100° C for three days is considered equivalent to 25 years of natural aging, six days to 50 years, etc.) Line “A” represents book papers made between 1534 and 1713; “B” representative modern book papers given a stabilizing treatment; “C” untreated modern papers with a rapid rate of deterioration.

Retention (percentages) of folding endurance (average for both directions) after heating at 100°C for from 1 to 24 days. A, Average for seven old papers made between 1534 and 1713; B, average for the papers shown as C after treatment with the bicarbonate solution; C, average for six untreated modern book papers with a rapid rate of deterioration.

mendations for making services of the Exchange more useful. These are being pursued by the Exchange in cooperation with the library associations and others which it represents.

In March 1959 the Council made a small grant to Harvard University on behalf of the Association of Research Libraries to make possible a "qualitative survey" of the holdings of American libraries in Russian and East European publications as part of a larger survey conducted by the Association, with assistance from the Joint Committee on Slavic Studies, of the resources of American libraries for such studies. The grant also provided assistance toward publication.

The report, actually constituting a published book providing a guide to present collections of material serving Slavic studies and providing also the elements of a national plan for their future development, has been issued by the Columbia University Press²².

A Permanent and Durable Book Paper. Following the successful completion of the first inquiry into the causes of and possible remedies for the deterioration of book paper conducted by Mr. William J. Barrow under the auspices of the Virginia State Library in 1957-58²³ the Council made a second grant to attempt to implement the resulting suggestions and recommendations. The purpose of this second project was (a) to develop by testing the specifications of a paper which would have adequate permanence and durability for library use; (b) to ascertain whether such specifications can be met by available book papers; (c) failing this, to ascertain by experiment, employing the Barrow formula, whether such a paper can be made at a price competitive with commercial book papers.

The results of the project appeared in a report which came out just after the close of the year²⁴ It was found that no commercially available wood pulp book papers could meet

²² Melville J. Ruggles, and Vaclav Mostecky: *Russian and East European Publications in the Libraries of the United States*. New York, Columbia University Press, 1960. xv, 396 pp.

²³ III:32-32.

²⁴ Randolph W. Church, editor: *The Manufacture and Testing of Durable Book Papers, Based on the Investigations of W. J. Barrow*. Richmond, The Virginia State Library, 1960. 63 pp. And subsequently: *Permanent/Durable Book Paper, Summary of a Conference Held in Washington, D. C., September 16, 1960, Sponsored by the American Library Association and the Virginia State Library*. Richmond, The Virginia State Library, 1960. 53 pp.

HIGH DENSITY PHOTO-STORAGE—In the memory unit of the Avco machine the “store” is in the cubic-foot space bounded by the plexiglass plate seen in the center, and has a capacity of approximately 1,000,000 pages at 100-diameters reduction. The remainder of the equipment serves to locate a particular page in the store and project it for consultation in about one second.

reasonable specifications for permanence and durability. In consequence, a series of experiments, conducted at the Herty Foundation, Savannah, attempted to develop such a paper within the price range of commercially available papers. The attempt was successful and several experimental commercial runs of the resulting paper were made by the Standard Paper Manufacturing Company of Richmond and were successfully employed in publications, including the *Virginia Magazine of History and Biography*. It thus became possible to erect a feasible standard for a paper suitable in terms of permanence and durability for library use. At the end of the year the Council was planning ways for bringing this standard to bear upon the practices of paper manufacturing and book publication.

The results of these two projects, even if they should go no further than they have gone to date, may be regarded as constituting a remarkable achievement. A solitary worker — in this age of group research — unconnected with the complex technology and economics of paper manufacture and use, save as his interest in the subject was stimulated by his activities in document restoration, has in the short space of three years been able to concentrate attention on the causes of paper deterioration, to identify the principal target for attack, and to succeed in providing a feasible solution — commanding the respect of the experts — to a problem which has been for three quarters of a century one of the most stultifying and baffling that libraries have faced. The Council takes great satisfaction in having been able to support the work.

High-Density Photo-Storage. In December 1958 the Council awarded a contract to the AVCO Manufacturing Company for the design and construction of a working model of a device to test the possibility of photo-storage at high-ratio (100 diameters or more) microreduction.²⁵ The work was conducted at the Electronics Research Laboratory of the Company's Crosley Division in Boston under the direction of Louis H. Martin. Work under the contract was concluded in January 1960.

At that time two principal pieces of equipment were in operating condition: a step-and-repeat camera capable of photocopying at fixed reduction ratios between 70:1 and 140:1; and a microstore capable of holding up to approximately one million pages (at 140:1 reduction), of finding any stored page in 0.3 to 2.0 seconds, and of making the page available in the form either of a photographic enlargement (*e.g.*, on 35 mm. microfilm) or of a screen-size televised image. The televised image would be initially controlled by direct scanning of the optical image projected from the store, but, when desired, control could be transferred to an electrostatic storage tube, freeing the direct scanning mechanism to serve other users.

A major defect of the system at the point described was that it lacked a method of providing "hard copy" without the delay required for laboratory processing of microfilm. Just at this time, however, the Electronics Research Laboratory was discontinued, and the machine was removed to the company's main plant in Cincinnati, where further development, includ-

²⁵ III:34-35.

ing the provision of a dry-process "hard-copy" read-out, is proceeding.

Meanwhile, a report of the development to date provides not only a description but also a technical discussion of the optical problems encountered in any high-ratio photo-reduction²⁶.

What has been accomplished to date may be considered to be a first—though an important—step. There still remains the task, after completion of the development, of testing the application of the device, both in technological and economic terms, to an actual situation.

Copying Devices. Eugene Garfield Associates completed the work on the device ("The Copywriter") for which a contract has been placed in November 1958.²⁷ This is a mechanism intended to be used in situations where short passages, titles, bibliographical entries, etc., are to be transcribed selectively from among other text. The requirements for feasibility were (a) a scanning device which would isolate and transcribe the text to be copied, and (b) a method of recording which would not require laboratory processing. The working model incorporates these elements, making use of a photocell in the transcribing unit and of "Teledeltos" paper in the recording unit. It is able to transcribe lines of 10-point type at the rate of half-an-inch per second and of 12-point type at approximately twice this speed. While thus demonstrating the feasibility of the suggestion, it was found that further work is needed especially in reducing the bulk and weight of the several pieces of equipment²⁸. The Council has such further work under consideration.

Library Work in the Soviet Union. Several years ago, it became apparent that for want of good available descriptions of libraries and information work in the Soviet Union, much misinformation on these subjects was gaining currency derived from travelers' tales. The corrective to this, the Council thought, was to commission a study of the place of libraries in the infor-

²⁶ K. Bowker, L. H. Martin, E. J. Lucas, C. Phaneuf: *Technical Investigation of Elements of a Mechanized Library System, Final Report No. EW-6680, January 11, 1960.* Boston, Electronics Research Laboratories, Crosley Division, AVCO Corporation, 1960. vi, 110 pp. Processed.

²⁷ III:38.

²⁸ [Eugene Garfield Associates.] *Final Report on the Development of a First Model of the Copywriter.* Philadelphia, The Company, April 20, 1960. 11 ll. Typescript.

mational process in the Soviet Union based upon authentic published sources. In consequence, two works were sponsored, one on libraries and one on publishing²⁹. Both have been the recipients of favorable reviews.

APPENDIX A

SEARCHING FOR AN INEXPENSIVE HAND-READER FOR MICROTEXT

The following is a case history, drawn from the Council's files, recording the not untypical progress of development of a device for use in library work.

Nearly 3,000 years ago the Chaldeans made use of magnifying glasses and "microtext." This we know on the evidence, found in the ruins of Nineveh, of a convex lens made of quartz and tablets with inscriptions too small to be read by the naked eye. Though progress has been made since the days of the Chaldeans, particularly in the past century and a half, the facilities for reading microtext are still far from perfect.

The situation was one to which the Council on Library Resources addressed itself early in its career and has continued to give attention. What could be done to increase the usefulness of microtext in library work? The microforms (microfilm, Microprint, Microcards, Microlex, microfiches) perform important functions for libraries and their users, but as with most advances they have created new problems in the solving of older ones.

An outstanding problem has been the inability of the individual user to make convenient use of microtext. To use it he must typically go to an expensive, stationary reading device provided for the purpose by the library. This may or may not be in a convenient location; in any case he is required to go to the machine rather than work in a location of his choice. While this situation may be tolerable for extended searches

²⁹ Paul L. Horecky: *Libraries and Bibliographic Centers in the Soviet Union*. [Bloomington, Indiana University Publications, c 1959] xviii, 287 pp. (Slavic and East European Series, vol. 16.) Boris I. Gorokhoff: *Publishing in the U.S.S.R.* [Bloomington, Indiana University Publications, c 1959.] xvi, 306 pp. (Slavic and East European Series, vol. 19.)

PROTOTYPES — Stages in research are represented by these models of hand readers for microtext.

Figure 13 — A tripod model.

(such as in microfilmed newspapers, Microprints of long series of Parliamentary papers, etc.) it is restrictive in other situations where more casual reference is involved. Furthermore, the researcher cannot take the device home, and the reading of microtext consequently becomes a library-related exercise, restricted in its utility.

It seemed clear to the Council that the usefulness of microtext, both to the individual reader and to the library, would be enhanced if there were available an inexpensive, portable hand-reader which would free the use of microtext from the institutionalized device and make its use casual, convenient, and even pleasurable. In that case, libraries might be able to supply inexpensive and disposable copies in microform, and required reading of scarce and out-of-print texts in college and university instruction might be assigned and be effected with inexpensive and disposable microcopies.

The Hand-reader Situation In 1957

When in 1957 the Council began to concern itself with the reading of microtext the most nearly adequate hand-reader for microforms was the Microcard Corporation's Model A reader, selling for \$25 (Fig. 14). This is a monocular viewer with a 10X magnifying lens, equipped with two forms of internal illumination — a flashlight battery and bulb and an electric cord and transformer. This hand-reader made it possible to read Microcards with a degree of convenience. However, it fell short in several respects:

- a. It was monocular.
- b. Its lens was a 10X magnifier. This meant that in viewing a text which had been reduced 18X from the original, the perceived image was only 10/18ths — a little more than $\frac{1}{2}$ — the size of the original.
- c. The lens had insufficient "eye relief" (distance between lens and eye) to permit it to be used with eyeglasses.
- d. The device was constructed to hold 3" by 5" Microcards. In order to use larger cards it was necessary to lay the unit on the surface of the card.
- e. The illumination mechanism was cumbersome.
- f. The price, \$25, was not conducive to wide sale of a device so limited in convenience and usefulness.

In spite of these defects, it seemed worthwhile to attempt to adopt this device as a basis for seeking improvement. Consequently, the Council enlisted the cooperation of the Microcard Corporation in a series of steps to this end.

Ambient Light and Price Reduction

The first step involved simplifying the illuminating system. The transformer and flashlight batteries were eliminated and a 110 volt bulb was substituted. With the elimination of the batteries, the cast was redesigned. The resultant device is illustrated in Fig. 15.

The next step involved an attempt to dispose entirely of the necessity for internal illumination. It was thought that enough ambient (or "available") light could be secured from any well-lit room to do the job. The services of a designer of plastic optical equipment, the Newmann Engraving Company,

Detroit, were enlisted and a series of models employing plastic light collectors was designed (Figs. 7, 10, 11, 13, 16, 6, 4, 12, 5, 2). These models seemed to prove the principle of ambient light collection; with them the image became progressively brighter in an ordinarily well-lit room and comparably bright with the image obtained from the internally illuminated model.

It therefore seemed worthwhile to design a final model for convenience of holding and aesthetic experience, embodying the improvements. This is illustrated in Fig. 13, where the model is shown supported on a tripod. Further testing, however, revealed the fact that the plastic light collector served no genuine purpose. Identical illumination was secured with an air gap instead of the light collector! This discovery took the inquiry back to a point at which it had been a number of months previous.

At this point the Wildlife Disease Association expressed interest in experimenting with publication of a scientific journal, *Wildlife Disease*, in microtext and elected Microcards as the vehicle. The project, sponsored by the American Institute of Biological Sciences, eventually received joint support from the Council on Library Resources and the National Science Foundation.¹ A hand-reader was needed to make the project feasible. It was decided to use the Microcard Corporation's Model A, adapted as an ambient light reader in accordance with the findings above. The Microcard Corporation for this purpose produced a quantity of hand-readers from the same molds as the Model A, but cast in a translucent plastic so as to receive ambient light. The internal illumination apparatus of the Model A was eliminated. That it was possible to manufacture and sell this new model in lots of 200 at \$9.50 each represented a significant advance in the particular of cost.

Magnifiers, 20X to 12X

The search up to this point had produced two useful results: it had successfully substituted ambient light for a separately powered illuminating system and it had reduced the price of the hand-reader. But the hand-reader was still not good enough to effect the convenient use of microtext, which was the objective. Attention, therefore, turned to the lens.

¹ III:33-34.

The existing lens was an inexpensive, 3-element 10X magnifier. It had a field of view of 15 mm. (*i.e.*, the area which could be viewed through it had a diameter of 15 mm., or 9/16 in.). With this field it could view an entire page of a 6" by 9" book reduced at 18X. But the image of the page thus seen would appear, as previously stated, to have a size only a little more than half of the original. This fact, plus the fact that the image had to be viewed with one eye only, and without glasses, put quite a strain on the user. Under these circumstances one would use such a hand-reader only when compelled to do so — certainly not from choice.

While the ultimate objective seemed at this point to be a light-weight head-supported binocular device, providing magnification at least equal to the reduction of the observed micro-image, the obvious first step toward this objective was to increase the magnification of the lens so as to provide an image the size of the original text. Unfortunately, as the power of a magnifier increases, other things being equal, its field of view decreases. No magnifier existed with a power of 18X and a field of 15 mm. It was necessary to design one. The questions were: first, whether such a magnifier could be designed; second, whether, once designed, it could be manufactured at reasonable cost.

The services of the John R. Miles Company, optical designers of Skokie, Illinois, were secured to work on the problem. The aim was to secure a lens having 20X magnification with a field of view of 16 mm., eye relief sufficient to enable the user to wear glasses, and a working distance (*i.e.*, distance between the lens and the object) sufficient to permit ambient light to illuminate the object. Finally, the lens was to be constructed of as few elements as possible and of inexpensive glasses, in order to permit its manufacture at a reasonable price (set at \$15 or less).

Using electronic computers for their calculations, the Miles Company produced some 220 designs over a period of four months. Two of these designs seemed to have sufficient merit to warrant the construction of models (Figs. 8 and 9). But in spite of the skill in design, the models still possessed slight residual aberrations (mainly astigmatism) sufficient to nullify the advantage of their increased magnifying power. Still another attempt was made, aiming at a lower target in terms of magnifying power, but fuller correction. This resulted in a 13X magnifier which provides a good view of an 18-diameter

image but which may yet be manufactured at a tolerable cost (Fig. 1, where the magnifier is shown in a plastic holder).

Simultaneously, the Microcard Corporation had employed the services of the Institute of Optics, a research group associated with the University of Rochester, to attempt to develop an improved magnifier. By the summer of 1960 there were three available magnifiers: the original 10X three-element magnifier, the Miles 13X five-element magnifier, and the Rochester 12X three-element magnifier. It was obvious that the target was not yet reached. With any of these magnifiers the user is still asked to view, with one eye, a text substantially smaller than its original size. The design of a magnifier which would improve this situation had encountered obstacles both in the cost of design and in the unacceptably high cost of any lens which might result. Another avenue of investigation seemed to be indicated.

In September 1960, the Council placed another contract with the John R. Miles Company to design a viewer consisting of two lens systems (*i.e.*, a compound microscope, as contrasted with a magnifier). Simultaneously, the Council invoked the assistance of the Battelle Memorial Institute in an inquiry which would in the first place seek to identify, by research rather than by assumption, the sources of dissatisfaction and inconvenience in the use of microtext by individuals, and seek inventively to alleviate them.

These inquiries are now under way.

NOTE ON ILLUSTRATIONS

The scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the cover and title-page, is from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine . . .*, Paris, 1588. The "Description of the Process to be observed in making large Sheets of Paper . . ." reproduced on the inside covers and concluded on the back cover, was read by Benjamin Franklin before the members of the American Philosophical Society on June 20, 1788, was published in the third volume of the society's *Transactions*, Philadelphia, 1793, and the following year in London, in the first volume of *The Repertory of Arts and Manufactures . . .* Dard Hunter has described Franklin's paper as "the only strictly American contribution to the bibliography of papermaking" to appear in the eighteenth century. (Papermaking, *The History and Technique of an Ancient Craft*, 2d edition, New York, 1957, p. 235 n.) It seems not inappropriate to reproduce it in view of the contribution to the bibliography by Mr. Barrow described herein.

The catalog cards reproduced on p. 14 are by courtesy of the Library of Congress. The photograph on p. 19 is by courtesy of the Providence Journal Company, John P. Callahan, photographer; that on p. 18 by courtesy of the American Library Association's Library Technology Project; that on p. 26 by courtesy of the Colonial Studio, Richmond, Va., and the chart on p. 26 is reprinted with permission from *Science*, 129, April 24, 1959. The photograph of the high density photo-storage machine on p. 28 was supplied by the Crosley Division, Avco Corporation. The photographs of microreaders, p. 32 and p. 33, were taken by the George Lohr Studio, Washington, which designed this report.

APPENDIX B

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Accountant's Opinion

September 22, 1960

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc., at June 30, 1960 and the expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of such statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards, and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other procedures as we considered necessary.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

STATEMENTS OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

June 30, 1960

ASSETS

Cash	\$ 346,986
Investments, at cost (approximate market):	
U. S. Treasury Bills, due August 1960	293,363
U. S. Treasury Notes, 4¾% due August 1960	600,349
U. S. Treasury Certificates of Indebtedness, 4¾% due May 1961	497,656
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation	1,250,000
Accrued interest receivable and deposits	19,250
	\$3,007,604

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable, per accompanying statement	\$ 732,594
Accounts payable and accrued salaries	7,610
Fund balance:	
Balance June 30, 1959	\$2,884,423
Expenditures less income for the year	617,023
	2,267,400
Balance June 30, 1960 (including \$1,012,443 appropriated for certain grants and contracts)	2,267,400
	\$3,007,604

STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

For the Year Ended June 30, 1960

EXPENDITURES

Grants, contracts and Council-administered projects	\$ 569,211	
Less — adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded	35,262	
		\$ 533,949

General administrative expense

Compensation and employee benefits	\$ 100,511	
Rent	6,600	
Professional services	3,116	
Travel and meetings	10,577	
Furniture and equipment	959	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other .	13,680	135,443
		\$ 669,392

INCOME

From Investments		52,369
EXPENDITURES LESS INCOME		\$ 617,023

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1960

	Payable June 30, 1959	Grant, contract or project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1960
American Association of Law Libraries					
A mechanized compilation of a list of legal subject headings		\$ 5,000			\$ 5,000
American Institute of Biological Sciences					
Experimental publication of a scientific journal in microform	\$ 5,000			\$ 2,500	2,500
American Library Association					
Feasibility study of an exhibit of the "Library of the Future"		2,000		2,000	
Library Technology —					
A program of testing and standardization of library equipment, supplies and systems ..	101,395			25,000	76,395
Additional projects of testing library supplies, equipment and systems		5,000		5,000	
Development of a book-marking system		20,000		20,000	
Projects of testing and standardization to be submitted from time to time		100,000		9,000	91,000
Testing of adhesives, copy paper and film coatings		1,000		1,000	
Testing of certain materials used in book and manuscript repair and preservation		2,600		2,600	
Planning an investigation toward the improvement of metropolitan area library service ...		1,629		1,629	
A study of circulation control in libraries — expenses of advisory committee		6,800		6,800	
Study of the feasibility of developing a code for identifying current American publications ...		4,987		4,987	
Travel grants to promote international coordination of cataloging rules		5,700		5,700	
American Library Association (co-sponsor with Association of Research Libraries)					
Preparation of a book on the planning of college/university library buildings		85,365		50,000	35,365
American Council of Learned Societies					
Inquiry into the bases for planning scholarly photocopying projects		28,888		28,888	
A report on the acquisition of foreign publications under the provisions of Public Law 480		1,500	\$ 712	788	

	Payable June 30, 1959	Grant, contract or project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1960
AVCO Manufacturing Corporation (Crosley Division)					
Development of an experimental high-density direct-access photo-storage and retrieval system for library materials	117,853			117,853	
Bowdoin College					
A survey of possibilities of cooperation among principal Maine libraries		5,000		5,000	
Brookings Institution					
A survey of Federal Government libraries	34,978				34,978
Brown University					
A study in support of university-school-community library coordination		24,000		12,000	12,000
Cornell University (as fiscal agent for the Association of Research Libraries)					
Establishment of a formula for library overhead in government contract university research ..		3,000		3,000	
A study of bibliographical control of microforms		11,550		11,550	
The de Florez Company, Inc.					
Construction of a working model of an automatic book-cradle/page-turner		20,000		13,806	6,194
Development of an improved stencil duplicator for catalog cards		2,000		286	1,714
Development of a current-cumulative book-selection service for college libraries*					
		5,000	4,040	960	
Development of a program for establishing performance standards for library binding*					
		5,000	4,569	431	
John Diebold & Associates, Inc.					
Preliminary inquiry into problems of book-charging		7,000	593	6,407	
Emory University					
Preparation of a new edition of the Administration of the College Library		2,000		2,000	
Eugene Garfield Associates					
Development of an experimental model of the "Copywriter"	8,100	2		8,102	
George Fry and Associates, Inc.					
Inquiry into problems of book-charging		77,500			77,500
Image Instruments, Inc.					
First phase investigation of the applicability of electronic systems to library service in metropolitan areas		5,000			5,000

	Payable June 30, 1959	Grant, contract or project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1960
International Federation of Library Associations					
An international conference on the principles of cataloging, 1961		95,420		10,000	85,420
A preliminary meeting on the international coordination of cataloging rules, 1959			3,700	(3,700)	
Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials, Inc.					
Assistance toward placing the record of serials in libraries in the United States and Canada on a continuing basis (3rd Edition of the Union List of Serials , etc.)	244,651			100,000	144,651
Library of Congress					
Creation of a national union catalog of manuscript collections	100,000				100,000
A pilot study of the use of classified book collections		5,525		5,525	
Meeting of joint committee of the Association of American Colleges and the Association of College and Research Libraries*		1,500	883	617	
The Microcard Corporation					
Development of a head-supported reader for micro-opaques	3,500		3,500		
John R. Miles Company					
Development of a 13X magnifier for reading micro-opaques		5,175		5,033	142
Development of a 20X magnifier for reading micro-opaques	2,000		1,760	240	
National Book Committee					
A training program to assure continuity of effort toward the National Library Week Observance		10,000		10,000	
National Microfilm Association					
Demonstration of microcopying techniques, equipment and applications			4,670	(4,670)	
Osborn, Andrew D.					
Travel grant in connection with problems of cataloging and Australian/American exchanges of library materials		1,000		1,000	
Pan American Union					
A study of obstacles to the free flow of books (in the book trade) among the American Republics		1,000		1,000	
Princeton University (as fiscal agent for the Association of Research Libraries)					
Extension of the Farmington Plan for the Cooperative Acquisition of Foreign Publications ..	6,400			6,400	
Review of Council on Library Resources Inc., program*		10,000		6,450	3,550

	Payable June 30, 1959	Grant, contract or project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1960
Rutgers — The State University					
Targets for research in library work			5,231	(5,231)	
Sharify, Nasser					
A cataloging code for Persian materials	737		737		
Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.					
In support of an exhibit of the work of the Service		170	7	163	
Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc.					
Studies in word correlation and automatic indexing	68,216			51,631	16,585
United States Book Exchange					
A re-evaluation of the operations of the Exchange			1,851	(1,851)	
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	44,600			10,000	34,600
University of Illinois					
Computations connected with the 1960 census and its implication for libraries		400		400	
University of Michigan					
A feasibility study of "telereference"	63		9	54	
In support of the National Conference on the Undergraduate and the Life-Time Reading Habit			1,158	(1,158)	
Virginia State Library					
Improvement of permanence and durability of book papers	21,000			21,000	
University of Virginia					
The use of closed-circuit TV in a decentralized library situation			581	(581)	
Yakobson, Sergius, Boris I. Gorokhoff and Paul L. Horecky					
Preparation of a report on libraries in the infor- mation-dissemination process in the Soviet Union (supplemental)		1,500		1,500	
Toward publication of Libraries and Bibliographic Centers in the Soviet Union by Paul L. Horecky*	1,604		885	719	
Toward publication of Publishing in the USSR by Boris I. Gorokhoff*	1,180		376	804	
Yale University					
Development and demonstration of the basis, operation and results of the Yale University Library's selective book retirement program .	50,000			50,000	
Totals	\$811,277	\$569,211	\$35,262	\$612,632	\$732,594

*Council-administered project

42 PROCESS FOR MAKING LARGE PAPER.

5. When dry they are to be again pressed, or, if to be sized, they must be dipped into size made of warm water, in which glue and alum are dissolved.

6. They must then be pressed again, to force out the superfluous size.

7. They must then be hung up a second time to dry, which, if the air happens to be damp, requires some days.

8. They must then be taken down, laid together, and again pressed.

9. They must be pasted together at their edges.

10. The whole must be glazed, by labour, with a flint.

In China, if they would make sheets, suppose of four and an half ells long, and one and an half ell wide, they have two large vats, each five ells long and two ells wide, made of brick, lined with a plaster that holds water. In these the stuff is mixed ready to work.

Between these vats is built a kiln or stove, with two inclining sides, each side something larger than
than

than the sheet of paper; they are covered with a fine stucco, that takes a polish, and are so contrived as to be well heated, by a small fire circulating in the walls.

The mould is made with thin but deep sides, that it may be both light and stiff. It is suspended, at each end, with cords that pass over pulleys fastened to the ceiling; their ends connected with a counterpoise nearly equal to the weight of the mould.

Two men, one at each end of the mould, lifting it out of the water by the help of the counterpoise, turn it and apply it, with the stuff for the sheet, to the smooth surface of the stove, against which they press it, to force out a great part of the water through the wires. The heat of the wall soon evaporates the rest, and a boy takes off the dried sheet, by rolling it up.

The side next the stove receives the even polish of the stucco, and is thereby better fitted to receive the impression of fine prints. If a degree of sizing is required, a decoction of rice is mixed with the stuff in the vat.

Thus the great sheet is obtained, smooth and sized, and a number of the European operations saved. As the stove has two polished sides, and there are two vats, the same operation is, at the same time, performed by two other men at the other vat; and one fire serves.

Council on Library Resources.

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